

Coverage of DOAJ journals' citations through OpenCitations

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Abstract

Purpose

Citations are the pillar of academia. All scientific studies naturally refer to other works. The study aims to reveal the coverage, in terms of citations, of the open access journals in DOAJ according to the data available in OpenCitations. In addition, the study presents the quantitative status of the references between these sources and points out the trend of availability in the years.

Approach

We obtained the input data of our study from DOAJ and OpenCitations platforms by downloading the public data dump of DOAJ articles and the OpenCitations' COCI. In order to improve efficiency and avoid the long search time, we downloaded the entire dataset directly instead of using the API. We filtered these two large datasets by using Python Programming Language and several libraries. In the final step we carried out a visualization of the output data.

Findings

We analyzed the coverage of articles in terms of open access journals in DOAJ according to the data available in OpenCitations. DOAJ journals receive around 36 million citations and do approximately 113 million citations. 10,5 million of these citations involve articles published in open access journals as both citing and cited entities. Observing the change in the citations over the years, it can be undoubtedly stated that there has been a remarkable increase trend in the last 20 years.

Originality

In order to improve the quality of scholarly communication, the data related to citations must be open and accessible by everyone. DOAJ and OpenCitations are important infrastructures

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that provide citation data openly. By revealing the coverage of Open Access journals in the above-mentioned organizations and presenting the yearly trend of involved citations in DOAJ we may draw attention to the importance of independent OA infrastructure in academic publishing, and may provide important aspects on why scientific studies should be open.

Keywords: open science, citations, OpenCitations, open access, DOAJ, trend of availability

1. Introduction

Scientific works build on previous findings and other studies. Basically, science is a cumulative and comprehensive process by its nature. Making use of the knowledge and methods produced so far is a necessary and inevitable phenomenon that contributes to scientific development and accelerates this process. In this context, it is extremely natural and expected that scientific works refer to each other. Citations are fundamental building blocks of this activity. It is crucial for the development and the sustainability of scholarly communication that all data on citations are open and accessible. Before proceeding with the details of our study we need to explain some basic terminology to have a better understanding. In this context the brief description of open access and open science, which are two distinct terms with a strong connection, must be done.

Open Access is an approach where resources are freely available to those who seek them, and these resources are preserved under a license that allows for secondary usage (Watson, 2015). The main purpose of open access is to open the way for new scientific studies and inventions by presenting resources equally to everyone. Watson (2015) describes open science as the implementation of sharing all data and findings in a complete, accessible and open way that allows others to interoperate and build on it(p.1). Open science is inevitably the goal to be reached. Because in the current closed system, serious payments are made to publishers even though they do not produce any value other than "*typesetting and PDF generation*" (Watson, 2015, p.2) However, there are platforms that try to make science open and create value with the open access publishing model. One of these platforms and also the main subject of this study is DOAJ (Directory of Open Access Journals).

DOAJ is an Open Access journal database containing more than 17500 peer-reviewed OA journals in different fields, from all over the world and in different languages. DOAJ's aim is to improve the accessibility, validity, use and effectiveness of peer-reviewed open access journals in a global context, regardless of scientific field, country or language. It is managed

by Infrastructure Services for Open Access (IS4OA), a UK-based public interest company (DOAJ, n.d.). DOAJ follows the Budapest Open Access Initiative's description for involving an OA journal. *"By "open access" to this literature, we mean its free availability on the public internet, permitting any users to read, download, copy, distribute, print, search, or link to the full texts of these articles, crawl them for indexing, pass them as data to software, or use them for any other lawful purpose, without financial, legal, or technical barriers other than those inseparable from gaining access to the internet itself"* (BOAI, 2002, para.3). The sole restriction on reproduction and dissemination should be to provide writers control over the integrity of their work and the ability to be properly credited and cited. DOAJ provides the article metadata openly that can be downloadable from its website. Besides DOAJ, another platform that forms the basis of our work and serves the purpose of making science open is OpenCitations.

OpenCitations is an open infrastructure that aims to make scientific data accessible, especially bibliography and citation data. It was initiated as a one-year project under the direction of David Shotton from Oxford University. The aim of the project was to change the current state of academic publishing and scientific communication. A dataset named OpenCitation Corpus has been built in order to produce and share open citation data. OpenCitations provides many citation indexes by exploiting open data coming from other bibliographic databases. The largest citation index is COCI (the OpenCitations Index of Crossref open DOI-to-DOI citations). *"It is an RDF dataset containing details of all the citations that are specified by the open references to DOI-identified works present in Crossref"* (OpenCitations, 2022). In this study, the dump dated March 26, 2022, which is the most current version at the time of the study, was used. According to this version, *"COCI contains 1,294,283,603 citations and 72,268,850 bibliographic resources"*. The data in COCI can be queried by using the OpenCitations Indexes SPARQL endpoint. It is possible to retrieve data also by using the COCI REST API or by directly downloading it. Retrieving data is a crucial step for a citation-based study. Before getting deep into the data retrieval process, we need to clarify the concept of open citation.

How can we consider a citation as open? *"A bibliographic citation is an open citation when the data needed to define the citation are freely available, downloadable and reusable"* (Peroni & Shotton, 2018, p.4). According to Initiative for Open Citations for considering a citation open it must be structured, separable and open. The citation must be accessible by

programming, in a machine-readable format. In addition, the citation must be analyzable without having to access the cited sources, and must also be freely available and suitable for reuse. (I4OC, n.d.). Platforms such as DOAJ and OpenCitations provide open access to such data. Our study is also built on the data provided by these platforms. There are some studies based on DOAJ or OpenCitations data before our study. However, there is no specific study covering both fields in terms of citations.

Studies on DOAJ focus more on published articles and journals rather than citations. Yet there is a study (Saadat & Shabani, 2012) that focuses specifically on citation data. However, this study measures the value of DOAJ journals by comparing citations found in proprietary citation databases such as the Web of Science (WoS).

In addition to these, there are researches that analyze the published journals on a certain field of study such as economy (N M & Pujar, 2021). The main purpose of these studies is to reveal the approach of the relevant field to Open Access publishing by analyzing the annual trend and country origin. The study limits itself to English-language journals. Citations are not the main subject of the study, the number of publications is taken into account.

Additionally there is a very recent study on DOAJ that aims to assess the growth of OA journals based on DOAJ public data dump (Pandita & Singh, 2022). Pandita and Singh (2022) claim that with the growth of Open Access journals, some publishers are abusing the authors and the entire scientific environment by not applying any plagiarism policy and publishing articles without peer-review in order to receive Article Processing Charges (APC) from the author (Pandita & Singh, 2022, p.2). However, DOAJ has a high standard in terms of publishing. In addition to its own standards, DOAJ provides its users a feedback channel where they can notify DOAJ if they come across a suspicious journal (Laine & Winker, 2017).

Besides all the instances in the DOAJ-based literature we mentioned, our study focuses on the following research questions:

- Which is the coverage, in terms of citations, of the open access journals in DOAJ according to the data available in OpenCitations?
- How many citations DOAJ journals receive?

- How many citations DOAJ journals do?
- How many of these citations involve articles published in open access journals as both citing and cited entities? What is the trend (increasing? decreasing?) in time of the availability of such citations involving journals in DOAJ?

Based on our research questions, we adopted a methodology to answer the questions and carry out the study. We initialized the progress by collecting the input data coming from DOAJ and OpenCitations platforms in CSV and JSON formats. Data is directly downloaded due to citation quantity and long response time. This data was filtered with the help of Python Programming Language and various libraries. We visualized output data and discussed the results in the upcoming chapters of the study. The following figures are provided for a better understanding of the creation process of the citations.

Figure 1. Creation of citations

Figure 2. Creation of citations

From the very beginning to the end of the study, each step has been published in open access resources including its different versions. We prepared a guide to ensure the reproducibility of our work by publishing a protocol in which we transparently convey all the steps of our work. The whole data involved process is structured by the help of a data management plan (DMP) that is deposited on Zenodo.²

2. Materials and methods

In our study, open science is not just our domain of interest but it is also the mentality that we equipped during the whole process. From the very beginning of the study we followed FAIR data principles. We aimed to make our data findable, accessible, interoperable and reproducible. In order to manage these goals we used several open access platforms such as Zenodo, Protocols.io and OpenAIRE. For providing solutions to our aforementioned research questions we initialized the process with the data coming from DOAJ and OpenCitations. We downloaded the public data dump of DOAJ articles³ and journals⁴ in .tar.gz format and the public data dump⁵ of OpenCitations' COCI in zipped files which contain several CSV files. We did not deal with any issues downloading data from DOAJ however, we faced some

² <https://zenodo.org/record/6491184#.Ys7YDZHxPY>

³ <https://doaj.org/public-data-dump/article>

⁴ <https://doaj.org/public-data-dump/journal>

⁵ <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.6741422.v14>

issues with COCI. There were two possible approaches to obtain the data from COCI. The first method was using the API service that OpenCitations provides. The DOIs that come from DOAJ are around 5 million. When we consider that each request containing a DOI addressed to the OpenCitations API, takes an average of 1,2 seconds to return a response, which makes it quite long to conclude the collection of the data necessary for the research in term efficiency. In addition to API, OpenCitations also provides a SPARQL endpoint which again would not be suitable for our research because of the efficiency issue. In fact, this system has much longer response times than the API, although it allows for greater flexibility in research. Because of these reasons we decided to download the entire dataset directly. One of the key aspects in determining our methodology has been efficiency. The main problem of downloading the entire dataset was the amount of data that will be preserved on the hard drive. Especially if one tries to read the data by unzipping the content. Instead of using more expensive components like RAM, we chose to use a hard disk because it is more cost-effective.

2.1 Gathering DOAJ Data

We use the DOAJ dump to generate a unique identifier for each journal by concatenating the issn and eissn. This unique key has the following values: the issn (if available), the eissn (if available), the journal title, the journal subject, and a list of all the article DOIs.

Once we open the tarfile with the data, we extract the issn and eissn information for each journal, but only if at least one of those two values exists for each journal record in the dump. Next, we add our "issn+eissn" unique identifier to the set of journals.

We extract data for the articles by opening the tarfile and then collecting the issn, eissn, and DOI for each article from the journal that published it.

If an article does not have a registered DOI, we add it to a separate list. Otherwise, we handle cases where the issn and eissn have been improperly recorded in the articles dump by aligning the data with the set of journals we created earlier.

We also gather the subject of the journal. After collecting all the information, we add it to our final json file. If a key does not exist, we create it. Otherwise, we add the information to the list of dois for that journal. Here is an example of an element in the final file:

```

{
  "1779-627X1779-6288": {
    "title": "International Journal for Simulation and Multidisciplinary Design
Optimization",
    "pissn": "1779-627X",
    "eissn": "1779-6288",
    "subject": [
      {"code": "T55.4-60.8", "scheme": "LCC", "term": "Industrial engineering.
Management engineering"},
      {"code": "T11.95-12.5", "scheme": "LCC", "term": "Industrial
directories"}]
    "dois": [
      "10.1051/ijsmdo:2008025",
      "10.1051/smdo/2019012",
      "10.1051/smdo/2020004",
      "10.1051/smdo/2020001",
      "10.1051/smdo/2016003",
      ...
    ]
  },
  ...
}

```

Figure 3. An example of an element in the doi.json

The aforementioned step produce the following files: **doi.json** and **articles_without_dois.json**. Then we generate a file that has a dictionary with DOIs for all DOAJ articles as keys, and the 'issn+eissn' identifier of the journal that published the article as the value. This will make the next steps simpler.

2.2 Gathering OpenCitations Data

In the step of our data gathering and filtering process from OpenCitations, we obtain data from the download section on the OpenCitations website then we refine and filter this data using the files we obtained in the previous step. The expected outcome of this step is a file called **by_journal.json** and it contains all the information extracted by Open Citations about DOAJ journals, organized by year and journal name. The researcher can find the following fields in this file: A group of fields that describe the selected journal, the journal's code (obtained by combining the journal's ISSN and EISSN), the year that all the citations' metrics belong to, the number of citations received, the number of citations done, the ratios between citations done and received, the number of citations received from other DOAJ journals, the

number of citations done to other DOAJ journals, the ratios between citations done and received from and to DOAJ journals.

A file that is created in this step is called **normal.json**. This file contains all the information extracted from Open Citations about DOAJ journals, divided only by year. The file includes fields for the year that the citations' metrics belong to, the number of citations received and done, the ratios between citations done and received, the number of self-citations made by DOAJ within Open Citations, and the ratio between the self-citation and the total citations received and done by DOAJ.

Another file created in this step is called **errors.json**. This file contains all the errors that were generated during the computations. The file includes fields for errors related to records that do not have a specified date (null dates), errors related to records that have impossible dates (wrong dates), errors related to articles that do not have a specified DOI, and errors related to Open Citations records that do not have a DOI in the citing or cited fields.

The final file created in this step is called **DOAJ_metrics.json**. This file will contain metrics about DOAJ and Open Citations, obtained through computations. The file will include fields for the number of journals with DOIs, the number of articles that were processed during the computations, the number of used DOIs (with no repetition), the number of repeated DOIs, and the number of accepted DOIs (which are articles that have both a defined journal and a defined DOI, with repetition).

2.3 Filtering OpenCitations Data

In the filtering we iterate through all the records in the Open Citations dump that have at least one DOI in either the citing or cited column. For each record firstly we unpack all the zip directory files into a temporary folder, and then iterate through all the unzipped CSV files. Then we split the CSV file into two dataframes. For each dataframe, we delete all the records that have a null value in the citing or cited column. In the next step, for each dataframe, we filter out all the records that have a DOAJ doi in either the citing or cited column. Then we add the journal name that matches the DOI in the citing or cited column. Additionally, we add a column for both the cited (`isDOAJ_cited`) and the citing column (`isDOAJ_citing`), to identify which doi belongs to DOAJ for each record (only the one in the cited column, the one in the citing column, or in the dois in both columns). We merge the two dataframes into a single one using an outer join. The expected results of the process are the following:

null_citing, a directory containing all files that have a null value in the citing column; **null_cited**, a directory containing all files that have a null value in the cited column; and **filtered**, a directory containing all files that have been filtered based on both the citing and cited columns, and that have at least one DOI from the DOAJ journals dump.

In the following step we iterate through each file in the filtered directory, and for each one we do the following:

1. Transform the creation column into a date format;
2. Save and discard all the records that don't have any creation dates or have a date after 2024;
3. Split the main dataframe into two sub-dataframes: one for the `groupBy` with only the year (`df_normal`), and another for the `groupBy` with both the year and journal (`df_by_journal`).

Expected results of this step are the following: **normal**, **by_journal**, **null_dates**, **wrong_dates**. The **normal** directory contains files that match those in the filtered directory. Each file in the repository groups together the corresponding files from the filtered repository and lists the following fields: year, number of citations received by DOAJ in Open Citations (cited), number of citations made by DOAJ in Open Citations (citing), and number of self-citations by DOAJ in Open Citations (self-citations). The **by_journal** directory contains files that match those in the filtered directory. Each file in the repository groups together the corresponding files from the filtered repository and lists the following fields: year, journal code (ISSN + EISSN), number of citations received by the DOAJ journal in Open Citations (cited), number of citations made by the DOAJ journal in Open Citations (citing), number of self-citations by the DOAJ journal in Open Citations (self-citations), number of citations made by the DOAJ journal to another DOAJ journal in Open Citations (citations to DOAJ), and number of citations received by the DOAJ journal from another DOAJ journal in Open Citations (cited by DOAJ). The **null_dates** directory will contain files that have a null date in the creation column, while the **wrong_dates** directory will contain files that have a date greater than or equal to 2025 in the creation column.

2.4 Concatenating Data

In the concatenation step of the study, we use the Pandas library to concatenate all the files in the **normal** and **by_journal** repositories into two dataframes, in order to summarize all of the data in those files. We use information from DOAJ to add a group of fields to the `df_by_journal` dataframe, which provides additional useful details about the journals. Finally, we concatenate all error files into one single file.

The process produces the following results:

- `normal.json`
- `by_journal.json`
- `errors.json`

normal.json is a file that lists the following fields for each record: year, total number of citations received by DOAJ in Open Citations (cited), total number of citations made by DOAJ in Open Citations (citing), and total number of citations made by a DOAJ journal to another DOAJ journal (`self_citation`).

by_journal.json is a file that lists the following fields for each record: year, journal, total number of citations received by the journal in Open Citations (cited), total number of citations made by the journal in Open Citations (citing), total number of citations made by a DOAJ journal to another DOAJ journal (`self_citation`), total number of citations made by a DOAJ journal to another DOAJ journal (`citations_to_DOAJ`), and total number of citations received by a DOAJ journal from another DOAJ journal (`cited_by_DOAJ`).

And the final outcome of this step is **errors.json**, a file that summarizes all the errors that were found during the previous computation, including `null_dates`, `wrong_dates`, `null_citing`, `null_cited`, and `articles_without_dois`.

Next, we compute and add ratios to the final results. We add ratios to both the **normal.json** and **by_journal.json** files. Therefore, both files are updated with the addition of a ratio within the metrics.

We add the following metrics into the **DOAJ_metrics.json** file, which provides useful research information about the DOIs processed from DOAJ: number of journals with DOIs, number of articles that have been processed, number of unique DOIs, number of repeated

DOIs, and number of accepted DOIs (which are articles that have both a defined journal and a defined DOI, including duplicates).

2.5 Data Visualization

We use the plotly Python library to visualize our results in line, bar, and scatter graphs. We use a query on the `final_df_journal` data frame to identify the DOAJ journals with the most citations, references, citations to DOAJ journals, and citations from DOAJ journals. We store the results of the query in a new data frame called `final_df_journal_1`.

In order to better understand our data, we examine the most common subjects among DOAJ journals. We show this data using a line plot.

Figure 4. Timeline of the 20 most recurring subjects among DOAJ journals

To analyze the total citations made by journals, regardless of the year, we group the journals by title and sum the relevant columns. We use bar plots to visualize the citations data for DOAJ journals.

Figure 5. Bar plot of the 30 DOAJ journals doing the most citations

We repeat this process using scatter plots, which also include information about the number of articles per journal. This allows us to see the relationship between citations and the number of articles for each journal.

Journals' Citations and their Number of Articles

Figure 6. Scatter plot of the 20 DOAJ journals doing the most citations, with size by number of articles.

We use a line plot to examine the journals that have done the most self-citations by year.

Journals with most self citations

Figure 7. Timeline of journals doing the most self-citations since 2000

To compare the citing and cited of DOAJ journals over the last 20 years, we create bar plots that stack the two amounts in the same column. This allows us to easily compare the citing and cited for each year.

Timeline of comparison between citing and cited of all DOAJ journals in the last 20 years.

Figure 8. Timeline of comparison between citing and cited of all DOAJ journals in the last 20 years

We use a bar plot to show the timeline of the number of citations involving DOAJ journals as both citing and cited entities over the last 20 years, as well as the percentage of these citations

within the total number of citations. This allows us to see how the number of citations involving DOAJ journals has changed over time, and how these citations compare to the overall number of citations.

Figure 9. Timeline of number of citations both coming from and going to DOAJ journals in the last 20 years⁶

Figure 10. Timeline of percentage of citations both coming from and going to DOAJ journals in the last 20 years

⁶ Data dump includes the data until its publication. Naturally it is not complete. That is the reason the year 2022 is smaller than the previous one (2021).

We use a bar plot to display the number of errors we encountered during the project, divided into categories.

Figure 11. Types of errors and their count

We publish the JSON files on Zenodo and in our Github repository (queried folder), where they can be accessed by others. This allows others to easily access and use the data that we have collected and processed. A detailed version of our methodology can be accessible through protocols.io.⁷ The software that was produced as an outcome of the study is deposited on Zenodo.⁸

3. Results

RQ1: Which is the coverage, in terms of citations, of the open access journals in DOAJ according to the data available in OpenCitations?

The first table displays the data extracted from DOAJ for our research. The following results concern only articles with DOIs, so a total of 5,8 million articles. Total number of journals indexed in DOAJ is 17,570 and 12,708 of these journals have articles with DOIs.

Number of journals indexed in DOAJ	17,570
Number of journals having articles with DOIs	12,708

⁷ dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.n92ldz598v5b/v5

⁸ <https://zenodo.org/record/6573898#.Ys7W0nZBxPY>

Number of articles processed	7,442,904
Number of articles with DOIs	5,829,660
Number of articles without DOIs	1,613,244

Table 1. Data extracted from DOAJ

This second table shows the coverage of open access journals in DOAJ, in terms of citations extracted from OpenCitations, so the total number of citations and references of DOAJ journals. The citations received by the journals indexed in DOAJ based on OpenCitations are approximately one-third of the citations they made. And the citations involving DOAJ journals as both citing and cited entities are about 10 million.

Citations from DOAJ journals	112,833,189
Citations to DOAJ journals	36,048,741
Citations involving DOAJ journals as citing and cited entities	10,590,234

Table 2. The coverage of open access journals in DOAJ, in terms of citations extracted from OpenCitations

RQ2: How many citations DOAJ journals receive?

Among the over 36 million citations received by open access journals indexed by DOAJ, the following table presents the 10 journals receiving most citations.

Title	Number of articles having DOIs	Citations received	Citations received from DOAJ journals	Percentage of the citations received from DOAJ journals
PLoS ONE	265,300	5,860,172	1,482,782	25.30%
Nature Communications	35,566	1,279,905	267,674	20.91%
International Journal of Molecular Sciences	49,207	626,313	23,857	3.80%
PLoS Genetics	9,658	516,416	111,297	21.5%

PLoS Pathogens	9,554	486,266	131,821	27.1%
Emerging Infectious Diseases	11,960	446,807	100,010	22.38%
Molecules	35,459	440,722	132,214	29.99%
PLoS Biology	6,374	431,820	81,125	18.78%
Sensors	40,259	431,422	150,061	34.78%
Frontiers in Microbiology	23,013	379,363	130,222	34.32%

Table 3. 10 journals receiving most citations by open access journals indexed by DOAJ

RQ3: How many citations DOAJ journals do?

Among the over 112 million citations done by open access journals in DOAJ, the following table presents the 10 journals doing most citations.

Title	Number of articles having DOIs	Citations	Citations to DOAJ journals	Percentage of the citations done to open access journals in DOAJ
PLoS ONE	265,300	9,450,129	650,059	6.87%
International Journal of Molecular Sciences	49,207	3,524,355	399,889	11.34%
Scientific Reports	47,840	1,882,967	175,405	9.31%
Sustainability	46,149	1,776,121	184,593	10.39%
Nature Communications	35,566	1,730,563	114,636	6.62%
Molecules	35,459	1,660,000	152,189	9.16%
International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health	41,225	1,565,855	198,220	12.65%
Frontiers in Immunology	22,630	1,499,385	172,458	11.5%
Frontiers in Microbiology	23,013	1,264,777	159,413	12.6%
Sensors	40,259	1,169,834	140,058	11.97%

Table 4. 10 journals doing most citations in DOAJ

RQ4: How many of these citations involve articles published in open access journals as both citing and cited entities? What is the trend (increasing? decreasing?) in time of the availability of such citations involving journals in DOAJ?

As shown in the table for RQ1, there are over 10.5 million citations involving DOAJ journals as both citing and cited entities according to OpenCitations.

The graphs (*figure 7, figure 8*) included in the visualization section show the evolution of the availability of such citations over the years and the percentage of these citations.

4. Discussion

The Open Access ecosystem has grown over the past years. The number of OA journals and published articles is increasing. In the results of our research, we can clearly see the increasing trend over the years. When we look at the output data of our study, it is possible to witness an exponential growth in DOAJ citations, especially in the period between 2017-2020. The increase in the number of citations in parallel with the increase in open access journals and articles over the years indicates that the open access publishing model is gaining more significance. Despite this general growth in DOAJ, according to our results, there are no humanities and social sciences journals among the top 10 most cited academic journals. PLoS ONE is the leading journal with 265,300 articles with DOIs and with 5,860,172 citations received. 1,482,782 of these citations are made by journals that are indexed in DOAJ. In addition to PLOS One, PLOS publishing's other 3 journals are among the 10 most cited academic journals according to our results. These journals are: PLoS Genetics, PLoS Pathogens and PLoS Biology. They received 516,416, 486,266 and 431,820 citations, respectively. From this point of view, it can be said that PLoS stands out quantitatively among the academic journals indexed in DOAJ.

Similar to these results, in a study based on the period between 2003 and 2008, it is observed that PLoS is the second most cited academic journal in the field of natural sciences in DOAJ(Saadat & Shabani, 2012). In parallel with our results, *Molecules* is also among the top 5 most cited natural science journals in the aforementioned study. In addition to all these, another similar result is that the citations of academic journals in the field of natural sciences and health sciences are clearly dominant compared to the field of Humanities and Social Sciences. However, there is a clear difference between our study and this study. This study is based on citations from journals indexed in Web of Science, a closed citation database, to DOAJ journals. On the other hand, our work takes into consideration two open infrastructures, DOAJ and OpenCitations.

Another study, which was also mentioned in the literature review, has similar results in terms of DOI numbers (Pandita & Singh, 2022). According to this study, 11,403 journals out of 16,589 have a DOI. It constitutes 69% of all journals indexed in DOAJ. According to our results, 12,708 journals have a DOI out of 17,570. This corresponds to 72% of the total number of journals. Considering that the aforementioned study is based on the data dump dated July 21, 2021, there has been an increase of 3% in journals with DOI indexed in DOAJ in less than a year. From this point of view, we can assume that the majority of the new journals added in this process have DOIs.

In our study the analysis of the data that comes from DOAJ is limited with the entities that have DOIs. When we encountered missing data and errors in the data dumps, we collected the errors in separate files and published them. The file **article_without_dois.json** contains all the articles from the DOAJ dump that don't have a DOI registered. When analyzing our data, we saw that each journal always had at least an issn or an eissn, but some articles registered only one or the other while the journal data dump indicated both. In order to align the dumps and make sure to have no duplicates, we created a unique key for each journal by concatenating the issn and the eissn. Lastly, we found some errors in the COCI dump about the creation date of citations. For example, some were indicating years like 2109, or simply were null. We collected those citations in a separate file (**errors.json**) and published it.

OA has a number of issues facing it. Foremost among these are predatory journal publishers, who seek to gain financial gain by ignoring all ethical values in this field and abuse open access. The term predatory is used to refer to publishers who abuse the Article Processing Charges (APCs) received from authors (Laine & Winker, 2017). In order to get money from the authors, these journals publish without peer-review, without a comprehensive audit of the data presented by the article, even sometimes without a plagiarism check. One of the ways to identify predatory journals is the high difference between the number of citations the journal does and the number of citations it receives. In the data we obtained as a result of the study, we observed that some journals did not receive any citations, but they made a large number of citations. However, when we examined the aforementioned journals individually, we came to the conclusion that this situation is due to the fact that the current data has not been updated yet. In fact, DOAJ frequently inspects its database as a precaution against predatory publishers, and accepts and evaluates readers' feedback on journals they find suspicious. DOAJ has a seal for journals that meet all the requirements to be a fully open access journal.

About 1500 journals currently indexed in DOAJ have their seals. However, our research covers all the journals and not just the sealed ones.

5. Conclusions

We answered the research questions that constituted our initial case in the study. We have revealed how many citations DOAJ journals receive, how many citations they make, how many of these citations appear in open access journals as both citing and cited entities, and the trend of change in these citations over the years according to the data available in OpenCitations. The study shows an exponential increase in the annual trend of the citations.

There may be various reasons for this, some may consider that the evolving digital environment and developing opportunities are factors. However, this is not the subject of our study. On the other hand, it is possible to make some inferences based on the results of the study. The number of journals and articles published in DOAJ increases, and the number of citations received and made by DOAJ articles increases in direct proportion to this. As a result of the study, PLOS One, one of the leading publishers in the field of open access, is by far the first among the journals citing and receiving citations from DOAJ journals.

Out of 17.000 journals indexed by DOAJ, more than 12,000 of them have articles identified by DOIs and more than 10.000 of these are involved in citations to and from open access journals (in DOAJ). Within DOAJ, more than 1,6 million of articles do not have a DOI.

Although there are articles without DOI registration and incorrect metadata, DOAJ has an important function in open access publishing. These deficiencies can be corrected over time. Currently, the number of journals that fulfill all the requirements of open access and have the DOAJ seal is around 1500. It is possible to predict that this number will increase over time.

In the future, a detailed study can be carried out on the correlation and reasons for the increase over the years. In addition, a study can be carried out on how DOAJ takes precautions against predatory publishers and how these journals can be identified from the citation data.

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